

THE RECEPTION OF THE BAUHAUS IN CONTEMPORARY JAPAN

JUN ISHIKAWA

SUMMARY

What are we to make of the Bauhaus? This query has two principle aspects. One is the question of how its ideals, which have resonated globally as universal principles, have interacted with the unique ecologies, traditions, and aesthetics of specific regions. Another is the issue of how the "honest aesthetic" of modernism, with its rejection of superfluous ornament, can avoid falling into an oppressive orthodoxy and be successfully integrated into society. Mainly from the latter point of view, this paper focuses on the efforts of MUJI (Mujirushi Ryōhin, Inc.) as an example of an innovative effort to carry forward the ideals of the Bauhaus

in contemporary Japan. One of the greatest aesthetic achievements of the modernism pioneered by the Bauhaus was the discovery of space as protagonist or void as presence. MUJI, which has staked out its territory with paradoxes such as "design as non-design" and "brandless branding," has inherited this approach, as may be seen in its use of "emptiness" as an advertising concept. In the growth of MUJI, we may see the development of a keen perception of the wasteland of vanity that is contemporary society, and a sensibility that recoils at it, seeking to convert its very hollowness into a vessel that may receive the light of grace.

THE LIVING BAUHAUS, OR TRANSPLANTING AN "HONEST AESTHETIC"

In 2019, the centennial anniversary of the founding of the Bauhaus was commemorated in Japan in a variety of ways. The largest of these events was a traveling exhibition, *Kitare, Bauhaus: Zokei-kyoiku no Kiso (Come to Bauhaus! The Basis of Education in Art and Design)*, organized around the collection of residential housing manufacturer Misawa Homes¹ and supplemented by other Bauhaus-related works assembled from other collections in Japan.² As the subtitle suggests, the exhibition pivoted around the theme of education. The Bauhaus can of course be spoken of in terms of its ideals and intellectual history, but this approach—seeing it first and foremost as a school and attempting to grasp the realities of its education activities—

seems most reasonable. The structure of the exhibition was interwoven with a number of hands-on experiential learning corners for visitors, aimed at giving them a vivid experience of what it was like to take classes with the various Bauhaus masters. The interactive exhibits concerning color and the sense of touch were close to those one might find in a science museum, and drew the attention of visitors in a quite enjoyable way to the experimental spirit that suffused the Bauhaus. The exhibition also delved deeply into the accomplishments of four Japanese who were students there.

The end of 2018 saw the publication of a Japanese translation of a work whose original German edition was published almost half a century ago: Eckhardt Neumann's *Bauhaus und Bauhäusler: Bekenntnisse und Erinnerungen (Bauhaus*

and Bauhaus people: personal opinions and recollections of former Bauhaus members and their contemporaries, 1971).³ And in the autumn of 2019, *Was ist das Bauhaus? (What is the Bauhaus?)*⁴, an illustrated children's book exploring the architecture of the Dessau Bauhaus, was also published in a Japanese edition. Rather than seeing the Bauhaus in terms of the rather grand and idealized image it has acquired, both of these publications shared with the *Come to Bauhaus!* exhibition an effort to present a "lifesized" picture of this famous institution. Undeniably, the tendencies of recent Japanese culture to reject pedantry in favor of relatability and ease of understanding shaped the context for these enterprises. But what is most significant here is the way in which these tendencies were put to use in enabling a straightforward and unaffected appreciation of the sense of possibility and potential that inhabited the original Bauhaus ethos. We see this in the bold statement in *What ist das Bauhaus?* that "Basically, the Bauhaus was a kind of kindergarten for adults,"⁵ a sentiment also voiced by the renowned architect and critic Arata Isozaki (*1931) in his praise for the book: "Only people who retain a childlike mind should read this book. It will change how you view your surroundings. The Bauhaus was a handmade revolution."⁶ We are aware of the history: that the modernism pioneered by the fresh, youthful experimental spirit of the Bauhaus would later be altered and deformed by the oppression, expulsion, and the logic of totalitarian conformity. But when the Bauhaus was in its infancy, modernism was, above all, an "honest aesthetic"—an effort to shed illogical conventions in both creative work and the ethics of everyday life. To relinquish the defenses of traditional rhetoric and throw oneself into the challenges of the broader world. How could such an aes-

thetic be successfully integrated into society? This was the key question that the Bauhaus has posed to us for more than a century.

The Bauhaus was a movement for reform of arts education that gave perfect expression to the seeds of modernity in architecture and design; it was also a movement for social change whose basic precepts might be summarized as follows. One should strive to live a life of simplicity, freed of unnecessary ornamentation, for this would best embody an aesthetic true to the sensibility of the times and the issues of the present day. Living spaces constructed rationally and economically, yet brimming with vitality rather than grimly utilitarian, would serve as subtle and exquisite vessels for the essence of the human spirit.⁷ This was the direction that the Bauhaus envisioned for building a better world.

So it goes without saying that the role played by the fine arts—often sidelined in considerations of the Bauhaus as the mecca of modern design and design education—cannot be underestimated. For Walter Gropius, the first director of the Bauhaus, responding to the challenge of how aesthetics should be shaped in response to the industrial age did not mean a simple rejection of the traditional arts. In a postwar collection of his writings, *Apollo in der Demokratie (Apollo in the Democracy, 1956)*, Gropius described the role of the artist in the following terms:

In contrast to the processes of mechanization, the work of the true artist consists of an unprejudiced search for a symbolic form of expression of the phenomena of our life... His intuitive powers are the antidote to our over-mechanization.⁸

Work of Bauhaus artists such as that of Oskar Schlemmer (**FIG. 1**), who utilized the awkward movement of the human body rendered as inorganic forms to

Fig. 1
Oskar Schlemmer
Bright Group, 1928
watercolor and pencil on paper,
56.5×41.9cm,
Utsunomiya Museum of Art.
© Utsunomiya Museum of Art

bring to mind the hesitant first stages of a relationship, conveys something essential regarding the role of the artist at the Bauhaus. The Bauhaus, while deftly responding to advancing technology and the demands of capital, also contained elements that relativized these tendencies—always imagining how the new vistas opened up by these forces might best be used by humankind. This is one of the reasons that the Bauhaus has continued to be a vital point of reference through all the structural transformations that have taken place in post-industrial society, from the maturation of consumer culture to the penetration of digital media and the spread of globalization.

THE BAUHAUS AND MUJI, OR THE PLEASURES OF PURITY

There was another noteworthy Bauhaus exhibition in Japan in 2019: *Archives: Bauhaus*, which was featured at Atelier MUJI Ginza, a gallery space in the new MUJI store in the Ginza district of Tokyo, from June through September.

MUJI Ginza had just opened in April 2019 as the flagship store of the global retail chain Mujirushi Ryōhin, better known as MUJI. The Ginza store overflows with the wide range of goods purveyed by this brandless brand, encompassing clothing, sundries, sta-

tionery, furniture, home appliances, and even housing—and also incorporates a diner and delicatessen, a bookstore curated to reflect the brand image, a hotel, and a library. MUJI Ginza is a clear embodiment of the company's ethos in a unified architectural space: an effort to encompass the totality of daily life, transcending individual product options to comprehensively address every aspect of its customer's lifestyle. MUJI's catchphrase is "A simple, pleasant life." Its stance is one of focusing on pure essentials, avoiding the showy while at the same time not appearing cheap or drab, aiming at a quality of life akin to the feel of fine organic cotton. Embedded in this concept of "a simple, pleasant life" is also an effort to fulfill the ethical imperative to reduce one's burden on the global environment—or at least lessen the feelings of guilt. The soothing strains of Celtic music streaming through the store seem consistent with these aspirations. Perhaps we can see in this a relatively mature example of the socialization of the "honest aesthetic" touched upon earlier. But of course therein also lies a tacit acceptance of the premise that the socially transformative ideals of the Bauhaus should not be too loudly advertised if they are to take root in contemporary Japan.

In the exhibition, Bauhaus and MUJI products were displayed side by side, clearly positioning the latter as an inheritance and further development of the former. MUJI has also collaborated with the German manufacturer Thonet to market redesigned versions of classic modernist steel-tube furniture by Marcel Breuer, the renowned Bauhaus designer. A comparison of the original (**FIG. 2**) with the redesign (**FIG. 3**) reveals that while the fundamental structure of the original has been preserved, in both the proportions and character of the surface finishes the redesign has consciously

Fig. 2
 Marcel Breuer
 Armchair B34 (Variant Model), 1930/31
 tubular steel (chrome plated), fabric
 (Eisengarn), wood (painted), 86x58.5x69cm,
 manufactured by Thonet,
 Vitra Design Museum.
 © Vitra Design Museum, Foto: Jürgen Hans.
 Courtesy: Thomas Breuer / CCMHT.

Fig. 3
 Konstantin Grcic
 Armchair, 2008
 tubular steel (epoxy resin coated),
 fiberboard (urethane resin coated),
 71x51x55,5cm, manufactured by Thonet for
 MUJI
 Photo: A. Laurenzo
 Die Neue Sammlung – The Design Museum.
 © Pinakothek der Moderne

-muted its sleek elegance, creating a more simple and straightforward utilitarian feel. This could be seen as a product of a playful but carefully restrained dialog with design history, but we should also note that compared to quite expensive literal reproductions of these historic masterpieces, the MUJI-Thonet redesigns have managed to clearly draw the line between themselves and mere imitation, while at the same time being offered at affordable prices.

The Bauhaus and MUJI share a stripped-down aesthetic, product consistency achieved through standardization, and a wide range of extensibility. The Japanese company name Mujirushi Ryōhin (無印良品) literally means “no brand, quality goods” but the romanized abbreviation MUJI can also be understood in Japanese as *muji* (無地), signifying “plain,” as in cloth without pattern or decoration.⁹ In common with the Bauhaus, MUJI fundamentally rejects decoration or embellishment. Moreover, the corporate strategy of the “brandless brand”—in other words, finding individuality and product differentiation precisely in ruthlessly paring away all extraneous elements of what is normally conceived as “added value”—resonates with the paradoxical “styleless style” embodied in the Bauhaus as the “zeroth degree” of

modern design.

Even so, we cannot overlook the fact that major differences are revealed between the two in their approaches to achieving not merely a stripped-down simplicity, but one that reconciles purity with pleasure—or, to put it another way, how to solve the puzzle of eliminating extraneous elements while still leaving comfortable breathing room.

The wall-mounted CD player by MUJI advisory board member and product designer Naoto Fukasawa (*1956) may serve as a well-known example (FIG. 4). It resembles a fan, and the user quickly intuits how to turn it on: you give a tug on the little grip on the power cord dangling from it. With the same gesture used to start a wall-mounted fan, the CD begins to revolve, and music fills the room like a breath of fresh air. This subconscious connection is an integral part of the design, and the success of this visual and perceptual rhyme arises from the way in which it, too, breathes fresh air into what might have been an otherwise stiflingly minimalist formal geometry. It also might be considered as a distillation of how difficult it is to succeed with reticence. In an article which touches on the Bauhaus, Fukasawa writes of “bowing down before Breuer’s table” in acknowledgment of its perfection, but adds

Fig. 4
Naoto Fukasawa
Wall mounted CD Player (MUJI), 1999
ABS resin, 17.2×17.2×4.1cm.
Photo: Jun Ishikawa
Private Collection.

somewhat tersely, “I think my own design is a bit more relaxed.”¹⁰ The Japanese word he uses, *ii kagen*, can have negative or positive connotations, but here Fukasawa clearly does not mean arbitrary or sloppy, but something more comfortable and free-breathing, with the hint of a smile. And it is the pursuit of this elusive quality that is perhaps a point of pride among designers taking on the contemporary world.

The centennial exhibitions *Come to Bauhaus!* and *Archives: Bauhaus* are in fact heirs to two exhibitions mounted a quarter of a century ago: *Bauhaus: Geijutsu kyōiku no kakumei to jikken* [*Bauhaus: Revolution and Experiment of Arts Education*] in 1994, and *Bauhaus 1919–1933* in 1995. The first, mounted by the Kawasaki City Museum, was also the first major public showing of elements of the Misawa Homes collection. The second, which succeeded in providing a complete picture of the Bauhaus’ history

by featuring a wide variety of objects on loan not only from Misawa Homes but also from collections in Berlin, Dessau, and Weimar, was mounted by the Sezon Museum of Art (closed 1999), an institution that at the time shared the same corporate umbrella as MUJI—the Sezon Group, a conglomerate headed by the entrepreneur Seiji Tsutsumi (1927–2013), who was also active as a poet and novelist under the pen name Takashi Tsujii. It was Tsutsumi who launched the Mujirushi Ryōhin project in 1980, assisted by a brain trust that included the graphic designer Ikkō Tanaka (1930–2002) and creative director Kazuko Koike (1936–), aiming at an unabashed simplicity of design and presentation. The 1995 exhibition, comprising some 650 works and published in a massive 425-page catalogue, was unusually large-scale by Japanese standards, not just 25 years ago, but even today. The depth of the Sezon Group’s commitment to this exhibition is vividly indicative of the degree to which the Bauhaus served as an important reference in the group’s pioneering innovations in corporate cultural activities. It was also in 1995 that MUJI began marketing household appliances. There is no question that the years 1994 and 1995 were epochal ones in the reception of the Bauhaus in contemporary Japan.

SPACE AS PROTAGONIST, OR A BULWARK AGAINST INFINITY

In 1934, Kōtarō Migishi (1903–34) painted *Umi to shakō* (*The Sea in Slanting Light*) (FIG. 5), a work highly esteemed as one of the fruits of the reception of Surrealism in Japan. That same year, he was building a new atelier, but he died suddenly at the age of 31 before ever seeing its completion. The studio was designed by Iwao Yamawaki (1898–87), soon after his return to Japan in 1932 from study abroad at the Bauhaus.¹¹ The atelier

Fig. 5
Kōtarō Migishi
The Sea in Slanting Light 1934
oil on canvas, 162×130.9cm,
Fukuoka Art Museum collection.

Fig. 8
Kōtarō Migishi
Flying Butterfly, 1934
oil on wood, 121.2×84.9cm,
Migishi Kotaro Museum of Art, Hokkaido.

Fig. 6
Iwao Yamawaki
Migishi Atelier, 1934
Kōtarō Migishi memorial exhibition held in
the atelier, November 1934.

Fig. 7
Marcel Breuer
Chair B33, 1927/28
tubular steel (chrome plated), fabric
(Eisengarn), 83.7×49×64.5cm,
manufactured by Thonet,
Vitra Design Museum.
© Vitra Design Museum, Foto: Jürgen Hans.
Courtesy: Thomas Breuer / CCMHT.

(FIG. 6), impressive for the modernist vocabulary of its broad wraparound glass windows and spiral staircase with its sinuous lines and planes, was outfitted with steel-tube furniture that looked like it had come straight from the Bauhaus (FIG. 7). Probably in anticipation of hanging it in this new space, Migishi himself designed a steel-tube frame for another 1934 painting, *Tobu chō* (*Flying Butterfly*) (FIG. 8). In this work, a number of butterflies are pinned in rows in a specimen case, but the one at the upper right has somehow freed itself and is taking wing,

about to float off into limitless space. The playfulness of this extraordinary flight, executed with a kind of quiet matter-of-factness, somehow magically matches the subtly springy sensation of sitting in one of these cantilevered steel-tube chairs

According to the classification of “isms” we learn from textbooks, Surrealism and the Bauhaus are fundamentally different animals. And from that point of view, Migishi’s uninhibited blending of

Fig.9
 Marcel Breuer
A Bauhaus-Film, 1926 (from the magazine
 Bauhaus, vol.1)
 offset lithograph, 42x29.7cm,
 Bauhaus-Archiv Berlin.

the two might be diagnosed as nothing more than an indiscriminate love of novelty. But I would like to consider it as evidence that Migishi's distance from Europe actually enabled him to relativize its "isms" and more accurately draw forth the common elements animating the modernist spirit. But what were these elements?

Umi to shakō references the myth of Venus rising from the waves. As if in a Magritte painting, the goddess of beauty has her face shrouded in cloth,¹² rendering her anonymous and impersonal. Next our eyes are drawn to the riot of shells on the beach. These empty shells are the cast-off husks of life, and the life which has departed them might be symbolized by the image of the butterfly. Most of us have probably noted at one time or another the resemblance between the symmetries of bivalve shells and butterflies. Most of the shells in the painting lie face up, emphasizing their emptiness. Each of the shells appears to embody a small piece of the vaster emptiness that forms the picture plane as a whole, or perhaps to be singing its praises. In the brilliant light illuminating the beach, their chorus of emptiness echoes over the faintly colored sand.

"Resilient sound / A sky like the transparent sea," "Life begins from nothingness," "The atelier, devoid of anything but the movement of its own volume / Resembles a vacuum."¹³ These lines, from a long poem entitled "*Chō to kaigara*" (*shikakushi*) (*Butterflies and Seashells (A Visual Lyric)*) contain images that appear to reference both paintings mentioned above, and are notable for the various shades with which they present the image of emptiness.

What Migishi seems to have instinctively glimpsed over the fences dividing all the superficial "isms" was this fundamental theme of emptiness that runs as a common denominator through mod-

ernist art. Many of the Surrealists were taken with images of empty blue skies and desolate expanses. On the other hand, the Bauhaus radically advanced the idea that space itself is existence. Marcel Breuer's proposition that "in the end we will sit on resilient air columns" might be seen as an extreme example of this (FIG. 9). This is the motif of his steel-tube chairs: the embodiment of emptiness in a physical object. When things are reduced to their essences in this way, space itself conversely takes on an independent and richly dense negative physicality.

The modern is an aesthetic arising out of a situation in which the key elements guaranteeing the operation of narrative as narrative, or meaning as meaning, are no longer operative. When the master to be venerated is absent, songs of praise deteriorate into empty rhetoric. But even when God is dead, the desire to praise and venerate something cannot be eliminated. Thus Gropius wrote in the Bauhaus Manifesto of "the crystal symbol of a new faith" (*kristallenes Sinnbild eines neuen kommenden Glaubens*).¹⁴ Crystal: transparent, hard, sensitive to light, refracting it into a rainbow of color. Imagine light falling into an empty space—an unmarked expanse of sandy

Fig. 10
 Marianne Brandt
Student on a Balcony of the Atelier Building,
Bauhaus Dessau, c. 1929
 Bauhaus-Archiv Berlin.
 © 2020, ProLitteris, Zurich

Fig. 11
Yukio Mishima on the Balcony of the Self
Defense Forces Building, wearing a uniform of
the Tate no Kai (Shield Society), 1970
 photograph of the Asahi shimbun.

beach, a wall, a floor—which subtly reflects the gradations of light as they change from moment to moment. In such moments, we can perceive the impersonal grace of that light. The emptiness of the space is precisely what makes it the vehicle to receive such grace. And therein lies the bliss of modernism, which starts from zero, embracing terrible loss.

Among the many attractive details of the Bauhaus Dessau campus are the balconies of the studio building (FIG. 10), with their almost dizzying sense of freedom, like springboards projecting into a newly discovered, shining, infinite space. But this image of balconies facing a magnificent void is one that for many Japanese may also recall a horrific event. In 1970, the writer Yukio Mishima (1925–70) led the members of the Tate no Kai (Shield Society), a private militia he had organized, in an occupation of the headquarters of Japan’s Self-Defense Forces in Ichigaya. After calling unsuccessfully from the balcony of this modernist building for the assembled troops to join him in a revolt (FIG. 11), Mishima committed ritual suicide. Mishima was known as a gorgeous prose stylist, but his rhetorical mania might be said to have been a kind

of armor concealing a bottomless void. Here is Mishima, invoking an image of crystal:

At that moment, a single wisp of hair slipped over her clear white cheek, and out of the fine-drawn corner of the eye a smile flashed in a spark of black fire. But the pure line of her nose did not move. It was as if nothing had happened. . . this fleeting angle of the Princess’s face—too slight to be called a profile—made Kiyooki feel as if he had seen a rainbow flicker for a bare instant through a prism of pure crystal.¹⁵

This crescendo of verbiage is carried off with Mishima’s inimitable elegance, but the more the words are polished to an exquisite luster, the more illusory their content becomes. And the last scene of the fourth and final volume of Mishima’s *Sea of Fertility* tetralogy, dated the morning of his death, is well known for its presentation of a nihilism so complete it leaves the reader speechless. “The garden was empty. He had come, thought Honda, to a place that had no memories, nothing.”¹⁶ At the end of the first volume of the tetralogy, *Spring Snow*, Mishima had already revealed it to be the beginning of a larger work whose title was

drawn from one of the most prominent features of the lunar landscape—a sea that, if reached, would prove to be a waterless vacuum, a sea of tranquility.

One of the oddest anecdotes related to the Mishima suicide incident, one of the deepest psychic wounds in Japan's post-war cultural history, involves the Seibu Department Store, the core of the later Sezon Group, where the uniforms worn by the Shield Society were made. According to Tsukumo Igarashi (*1933), who worked there at the time, the design of the uniforms was undertaken at the request of Mishima himself, who passionately insisted that “they must be the most splendid in the world!”¹⁷ Seiji Tsutsumi, then head of the Sezon Group, later recalled paying a condolence call to the Mishima residence the night of the incident, where Mishima's father chastised him, saying “My son is dead because of those uniforms you made for him!”¹⁸

Of course we must refrain from drawing a direct line from this episode to the founding of Mujirushi Ryōhin in 1980. Yet at the same time, it is not difficult to imagine that the Mishima incident might have given Tsutsumi impetus for some severe reflection on the nature of fashion and design. The designer Ikkō Tanaka served as MUJI's art director from the company's establishment until his death in 2002, when Ken'ya Hara (*1958) took over responsibility for advertising art direction, proclaiming “emptiness” as an advertising concept. He explained his methodology as “Presenting not a message but an empty vessel, establishing communication with the receiver by encouraging them to fill it with their own meaning.”¹⁹ Yet if we look at one of the actual manifestations of this campaign, there would seem to be more than a bit of rationalization in this explanation. An ad used by MUJI in 2003, shows a wide expanse of white with a clear blue sky

above it emanating a dawn-like glow, and an extremely small silhouette figure near the right edge approaching the small white letters “MUJI” appearing just above it on the horizon — this ad image is merely a vision of a vast expanse of emptiness. But wouldn't presenting the viewer with “an empty vessel” also imply some resonance with the emptiness inside the viewer, and a dream of turning it towards the light?

Mujirushi literally means no mark or no brand, but in it resides another level, which might be read as “the mark of nothing”, or “the brand of emptiness”. Emptiness is almost always ambiguous. It can easily and swiftly shift from pedestrian blankness to brutal nihilism. But with extraordinary delicacy, it can become a receptacle for a pure light from far away.

“The inaudible voice of God resembles the sound of the waves.”²⁰ As mentioned above, Seiji Tsutsumi was active as a poet under the pen name Takashi Tsujii. His *Washi ga ite (Mit dem Adler; With the Eagle)* is a collection of poems with titles drawn from works by Paul Klee. The line quoted above concludes the poem “Uchi naru hikari no seijō” (*Die Heilige vom inneren Licht; The Saint of Inner Light*) (FIG. 12), which also contains the following lines:

At first glance she seems angry
But she endures
Please do not ask what
If I had to tell you I might say grace
Concealed within her breast a vast
wilderness unfolds.”²¹

The author would like to emphasize that the interpretation of facts about MUJI in this paper is a personal opinion.

The reader's understanding will be highly appreciated.

Translated by David Noble

Fig. 12
 Paul Klee
The Saint of the Inner Light, 1921, 122
 color lithograph, third state, 31×17.5cm,
 Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, privat loan.
 ©ZPK, Bildarchiv

NOTES

1. In 1989, Misawa Homes began to purchase a body of Bauhaus-related works from collectors in Switzerland and what was then West Germany that has subsequently grown into a substantial collection of some 1,500 works of art and design and 1,200 archival documents. A notable feature of this collection is the large number of student works it includes, offering unique insight into the Bauhaus educational curriculum. Misawa Homes opened a dedicated gallery for the display of this collection in 1996, and since that time has shared the fruits of its research in a series of more than thirty themed public exhibitions. Awazu 1991.
2. Fukagawa/Somada 2019.
3. Neumann 1971.
4. Kern/Rösch 2014.
5. *Ibid.*, p. 53.
6. Isozaki's comment appeared on the advertising sash on the Japanese edition of the book.
7. Shūichi Katō (1919–2008), one of contemporary Japan's leading intellectual figures, touched on the Bauhaus in a 1996 essay entitled "Bahha, Barokku, Bauhaus" (Bach, Baroque, Bauhaus). After pointing out the relativism of the term
8. Gropius 1956, p. 191. Ise Gropius translation, p.7.
9. The MUJI appellation was first used in 1991 when the company opened its first overseas outlet in London in 1991, as an alternative to a literal translation of the company name. Later, in 2000, the company changed its logo, which until that time had been the four kanji for Mujirushi Ryōhin, to one which emphasized an all-cap sans serif bold MUJI accompanied by the kanji rendered in a much smaller font. Koike 2000, p. 82.
10. Fukasawa 2004, p. 121.
11. As a part of *Bauhaus: Open-End*, a centennial commemorative program sponsored by the Goethe Institute in Tokyo in 2019, there was a screening of *Two Houses* by Verena von Beckerath, a documentary film introducing the Migishi atelier (which still stands in Tokyo), and a house designed as a personal residence by the architect Bunzō Yamaguchi, a student of Gropius.
12. Hayami 2009, p. 254.
13. Migishi 1934, pp. 60-61.
14. Gropius 1919, p. 72.
15. Mishima 1969, p.18. Gallagher translation, p. 9–10.
16. Mishima 1971, p. 648. Seidensticker transla-

"baroque" with reference to historical eras, cultural spheres, and artistic genres, Katō compared Bach, the representative figure of what is known as Baroque music, to the Bauhaus, arguing that what characterized his art was not its ornamentation but its rational structure. Then, referencing a dialogue by the poet Paul Valéry in which the ancient Greek architect Eupalinos is said to have aimed at structures that would "move men as they would be moved by their beloved," Katō writes that Bach succeeded in this. Bach's music, like the architecture of the Bauhaus, imbued found in orderly structural geometries "the subtleties of human feeling" and "a restrained sense of the sublime." Katō 1996, pp. 367–81.

tion, p. 236.

17. Tsujii 2009, p. 133.

18. Ibid., p. 141.

19. Hara 2003, pp. 112-113.

20. Tsujii 2006, p. 32.

21. Ibid., p. 31.

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